

ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF BUILDINGS IN SMART CITIES IN INDIA

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Extended Abstract

1 Introduction

The concept of energy efficiency on an urban scale in buildings is a key aspect gaining importance in smart cities in India due to the rising demand for sustainable development. In the context of smart cities, energy efficiency refers to the ability of buildings to use energy more efficiently and sustainably, to reduce energy consumption, carbon emissions, and costs. Smart buildings are equipped with advanced technologies such as sensors, automated controls, and smart meters, which allow for real-time monitoring and optimization of energy use. These technologies can be integrated with other systems in the city, such as transportation, water, and waste management, to create a more holistic and efficient approach to urban sustainability. Energy efficiency in buildings can be achieved through a variety of measures, such as improved insulation, high-efficiency heating and cooling systems, energy-efficient lighting, and smart energy management systems. These measures not only reduce energy consumption but also improve indoor air quality and occupant comfort.

This paper aims to review the current status of energy efficiency in buildings in smart cities in India. The paper presents a comprehensive analysis of the key drivers and barriers to energy efficiency in buildings and explores the various policies and programs that are being implemented by the government to promote energy-efficient buildings.

2 Objectives

The paper studies the research works in Indian smart cities highlighting the importance of incorporating limited energy storage, heating & cooling technologies, use of smart building architecture techniques, low-scale implementation of innovative projects, and renewable energy sources in smart cities in India. It also highlights the insufficient knowledge and expertise for increasing efficiency in enhancing energy efficiency in buildings.

3 Literature review

(Mahesha et al., 2022) presents a comprehensive analysis of the key drivers and barriers to energy efficiency in buildings and explores the various policies and programs that are being implemented by the government to promote energy-efficient buildings. The paper highlights the importance of incorporating energy-efficient building design and materials, efficient heating and cooling systems, energy-efficient lighting, and renewable energy sources in smart cities in India. It also provides insights into the role of technology, such as building automation systems, in enhancing energy efficiency in buildings.

(Rana et al., 2018) demonstrated that there are 31 impediments relating to governance, economic, social, technological, environmental, legal, and ethical issues that need to be addressed in order to increase the efficiency of Indian smart cities. The study sought to identify and prioritise the challenges associated with using the MCDM paradigm for simpler, better management. By using fuzzy AHP to highlight the significance of potential obstacles in a fuzzy environment, the current study aims to identify and prioritise smart city development challenges to assist policymakers in enhancing their sustainability in an Indian setting. Lack of connections between operational nodes for smart cities, local businesses' inability to compete to meet the challenges posed by the expansion of smart cities, and rising economic volatility and unpredictability are a few factors that could seriously hinder the development of smart cities. The general population lacks a thorough understanding of smart cities and how they will impact their quality of life. Anything from a lack of smart water metres in specific homes to a lack of citywide public Wi-Fi infrastructure could be blamed for this issue. Absence of ecological viewpoint in environmentally responsible energy consumption, lack of appropriate legislation, regulations, or guidelines for the development of smart cities, as well as a lack of communal living in creative and sharing cultures are noticed. One of the criteria used to assess the MCDM model is the absence of suitable laws, regulations, or guidelines for the development of smart cities.

One piece of literature that demonstrates the restricted use of smart building architecture methodologies in the Indian context is the IBDMA framework and its reference design, which were developed and evaluated for a smart building example scenario (Bashir et al., 2022). Five essential components make up the framework: facility, technology, information, people, and process. The reference architecture underwent five cycles of evaluation for the smart building scenario. The evaluation was carried out via the DSR method. The evaluation was carried out via the DSR method. The evaluation's results demonstrate how a structured framework like IBDMA may be useful for processing and assessing the near-real-time massive data streams created for smart buildings. It also shows how the proposed IBDMA framework may be used to autonomously monitor and control a variety of smart building components, such as IoT sensors and control systems, in almost real-time. Because it combines end-to-end

sensing, data management, and autonomous actuation capabilities with the capacity to do near real-time data management and analytics, the proposed IBDMA framework is distinctive in this regard.

(Dey et al., 2022) presented conventional energy resources like oil, gas, and coal are very important for the improvement of the economical conditions of the country. In this study, the renewable energy strategy for sustainable development is a key parameter for development. In energy technology storing natural resources is focused on shifting renewable energy technology like solar energy, wind energy, tidal energy, geothermal energy, hydrogen energy, and biomass energy. Renewable energy will account for 55% of the total installed power capacity by 2030. It is expected that by 2040, around 49% of the total electricity will be generated by renewable energy as more efficient batteries will be used to store electricity, which will further cut the solar energy cost by 66% as compared to the current cost. In addition, renewable energy has the potential to create many employment opportunities at all levels, especially in rural areas. The Government of India wants to develop a 'green city' in every state of the country, powered by renewable energy leading to economic sustainability. Therefore, technological innovation dampens renewable energy consumption in these economies.

(Ionescu et al., 2023) has proposed a scientific approach with the main goal of developing the concept of a smart city/smart community to objectively evaluate the progress of these organisational forms compared to other classical/traditional forms of city organisations leading to the low-scale implementation of innovative projects. Local GDP, Internet users, RDI, IoT, and Internet banking are the new indicators used for the comparison. According to the research, low-cost solutions have more advantageous elements than the other category, which suggests greater managerial and financial efforts as well as a better rate of welfare increase for urban residents. The research's potential applications are viewed as workable alternatives based on smart city development opportunities with medium- and long-term consequences on urban communities, economic sustainability, and urban development rates. This study can be used practically to develop and carry out wise public policies at the metropolitan level.

4 Conclusion

The review paper concludes by emphasizing the need for a collaborative approach between government agencies, building developers, and residents to achieve energy efficiency in buildings in smart cities in India. The success of energy efficiency in buildings depends on the awareness and active participation of all stakeholders. The paper recommends a roadmap for promoting energy efficiency in buildings in smart cities in India and highlights the potential benefits of such efforts, including reduced energy consumption, lower energy bills, and reduced greenhouse gas emissions. Overall, the research paper concludes that solar energy system planning can be an

effective and sustainable solution for cooling and heating in smart cities on an urban scale. The paper highlights the importance of incorporating renewable energy sources in the design and planning of smart cities to achieve sustainable energy usage and reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

5 References:

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